

ASSESSING THE IMPACT OF PRIMARY PERCUTANEOUS CORONARY INTERVENTION ON ECHOCARDIOGRAPHY AND ECG CHANGES IN ST ELEVATION MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION

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Abstract

Background: ST Elevation Myocardial Infarction (STEMI) represents one of the most serious forms of coronary artery disease. The objective of this study is to assess the impact of primary percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI) on echocardiographic and electrocardiography (ECG) changes in patients presenting with STEMI. The study aims to correlate these changes with clinical outcomes one month after the procedure.

Methods: This prospective cohort study was conducted at the Peshawar Institute of Cardiology from November 2024 to June 2025 on patients with a confirmed diagnosis of STEMI and presenting within 12 hours of the onset of STEMI symptoms. Demographic data, medical history, baseline ECG data and echocardiography data were recorded. Data analysis utilized SPSS. Numerical variables were expressed as mean \pm SD. Categorical variables were presented as frequency and percentages. Chi-square tests were used to compare survival frequencies, with $p \leq 0.05$ was considered significant.

Results: The total sample size included in the study was 400. The mean age of the participants was 57.22 ± 11.13 years. The mean heart rate and systolic blood pressure was 81.76 ± 13.69 beats per minute and 127.24 ± 20.87 mmHg. The PCI procedure was successful in 371 (92.8%) and the complications during PCI occurred in 52 (13%) participants. The mean baseline left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF) was $42.31 \pm 7.75\%$. A significant improvement was observed at 48 hours ($45.89 \pm 7.95\%$, $p < 0.001$) and at one-month follow-up ($48.29 \pm 8.17\%$, $p < 0.001$). Killip class was identified as a statistically significant predictor of MACE (odds ratio (OR) 1.672, 95% confidence interval (95% CI) 1.137 – 2.460, $p = 0.009$).

Conclusion: Early and short-term left ventricular systolic function significantly improves following primary PPCI in patients experiencing STEMI. Clinical and procedural hemodynamics are independent predictors of clinical outcomes.

INTRODUCTION

Cardiovascular disease accounts for the highest morbidity and mortality worldwide, causing most premature deaths and healthcare costs in this disease group (1). ST Elevation Myocardial Infarction (STEMI) represents one of the most serious forms of coronary artery disease, with acute coronary artery occlusion and rapid myocardial ischemia progression (2). Due to this type of coronary occlusion and rapid ischemic progression, STEMI is a medical emergency where time to diagnosis and reperfusion are crucial for identifying myocardial damage, retaining cardiac function, and increasing survival rates (3,4). While advances have been made, STEMI remains a significant clinical problem, particularly in developing healthcare systems due to delays in presentation and treatment.

The sudden cessation of blood supply to the myocardium occurs through ruptured plaque or thrombus formation in coronary arteries (5). Prolonged ischemia causes necrosis characterized by electrical, structural and functional changes in the affected myocardium (6). These changes are identified clinically and through diagnostic tests. Electrocardiography (ECG) serves as a quick, non-invasive method of detecting acute myocardial ischemia with ST segment elevation indicating transmural injury (7). Echocardiography identifies mechanical consequences of infarction (i.e. left ventricular (LV) systolic dysfunction and regional wall motion abnormalities (RWMA)) showing the extent of myocardial injury (6).

Primary percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI), when timely, is the preferred treatment for STEMI patients. PCI aims to restore coronary blood flow mechanically, salvage ischemic myocardium, decrease infarction size, and improve clinical outcomes (8,9). Studies show early successful PCI significantly reduces mortality rates, reinfarction rates, and complications compared to other reperfusion forms (8,10,11). Despite established evidence supporting PCI's survival advantage, research continues, especially regarding dynamic

assessment of heart reperfusion, function recovery, and early post-procedural changes.

ECG has proven valuable for identifying STEMI and evaluating reperfusion therapy effectiveness. Complete resolution of ST-segment elevation following PCI indicates successful myocardial reperfusion at the microvascular level (11). Conversely, incomplete resolution indicates myocardial ischemia or microvascular dysfunction, suggesting incomplete myocardial salvage; thus, post-procedural ECG changes provide a convenient marker of myocardial salvage and reperfusion success (12,13).

Evaluation of patients undergoing acute myocardial isthmus can be performed via echocardiography. Echocardiography determines left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF), providing a reliable measure of risk for poor outcomes, including death from heart failure, arrhythmias, or complications (14). Assessing LVEF provides information about regional wall motion abnormalities, infarct location, and myocardial viability. The magnitude of myocardial stunning and recovery potential can be assessed early through LVEF and RWMA changes after successful reperfusion and can assess reperfusion effectiveness (15). Monitoring echocardiographic parameters before and after PCI allows assessment of myocardial mechanical recovery through direct measurements.

While many studies investigate clinical outcomes after primary PCI, few have evaluated both electrical and mechanical changes and their relationship during immediate and short-term periods following intervention. Due to differences among patients in pretreatment characteristics, reperfusion timing, and limited healthcare access in some regions, studies evaluating functional recovery of myocardium and its correlation to ECG markers of reperfusion are needed for local context. Understanding these relationships may have clinical significance by facilitating early risk stratification and improving post-infarction care. The objective of this study is to examine the effect of PCI on changes in both echocardiographic and electrocardiographic variables in patients who present with STEMI,

and to investigate the relationship between echocardiographic and ECG findings and clinical outcomes during the first month after PCI, in an effort to provide insight into patterns of myocardial recovery and implications for prognosis.

Materials and methods

This prospective cohort study was conducted at the tertiary care center, Peshawar Institute of Cardiology from November 2024 to June 2025. Ethical approval was obtained from Institutional Review Board Committee (Approval no. IRC/24/102 on October 02, 2024). Written informed consent was taken from the participants. Participant confidentiality was ensured by assigning unique identification codes in place of personal information. The study was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki. The sampling technique was non-probability consecutive sampling technique. Patients aged 18 years or older with a confirmed diagnosis of STEMI, presenting within 12 hours of the onset of STEMI symptoms (e.g., chest pain, shortness of breath) were included in the study. Patients having previous MI or revascularization, chronic kidney disease requiring dialysis were excluded from the study. Patients with any contraindications to undergoing PCI, including severe contrast allergies, bleeding disorders, or inability to tolerate antiplatelet or anticoagulant therapy, with terminal illnesses or severe comorbidities, such as advanced malignancies or end-stage heart failure (NYHA Class IV), where the expected prognosis is less than six months, and pregnancy were also excluded.

Data collection

Upon receiving ethical approval, data collection was started with a pre-PCI baseline assessment, documenting demographic data (age, gender, BMI, smoking status) and medical history (e.g., diabetes, hypertension). Clinical presentation details, including symptom onset and chest pain characteristics, were also recorded. Baseline ECG was done to confirm STEMI and assess initial ST-

segment elevation, while echocardiography was done to measure LVEF and RWMA. After PCI, a post-procedure ECG within 24 hours was done to evaluate ST-segment resolution, and a follow-up echocardiography within 48 hours was used to assess early changes in myocardial function. Data on the PCI procedure, including vessels treated and any complications were also collected. At one month post-PCI, repeat ECG and echocardiography was done to assess further recovery, along with data on clinical outcomes like recurrent ischemia, heart failure, and major adverse cardiovascular events (MACE). All data was recorded using standardized forms and stored securely to ensure accuracy and confidentiality.

Data analysis

Data was analyzed on IBM SPSS version 26. Continuous variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Categorical variables were presented as frequency and percentage. Chi-square tests were done to compare survival frequencies. Survival frequencies were stratified by age and gender to address effect modifiers. Post-stratification, chi-square tests ($p \leq 0.05$) were applied.

Results

The total sample size included in the study was 400. The mean age of the participants was 57.22 ± 11.13 years. Among them, 309 (77.3%) were male, while 91 (22.8%) were female. The mean BMI of the participants was 26.68 ± 4.12 kg/m², respectively. The mean heart rate and systolic blood pressure was 81.76 ± 13.69 beats per minute and 127.24 ± 20.87 mmHg. Among these participants, 168 (42%) never did smoking, 94 (23.5%) were former smokers and 138 (34.5%) were current smokers. Diabetes was present in 133 (33.3%), hypertension in 182 (45.5%), hyperlipidemia in 151 (37.8%) and family history of coronary artery disease in 89 (22.3%). Killip class was I in 272 (68%), II in 87 (21.8%), III in 30 (7.5%) and IV in 10 (2.5%). The symptom to PCI time was <3 hours in 139 (34.8%), 3-6 hours in 163 (40.8%), and >6 hours in 98 (24.5%) participants. Infarct was anterior STEMI in 184 (46%), inferior STEMI in 153

(38.3%), lateral STEMI in 37 (9.3%), and extensive in 26 (6.5%) participants. The baseline RWMA was present in 363 (90.8%) participants.

The PCI procedure was successful in 371 (92.8%) and the complications during PCI occurred in 52 (13%) participants (Table 1).

Table 1: Baseline characteristics of the participants (n=400)

Variable	n (%) or Mean ± SD
Age (years)	57.22 ± 11.13
Gender	
Male	309 (77.3%)
Female	91 (22.8%)
BMI (kg/m ²)	26.68 ± 4.12
Heart rate (beats/min)	81.76 ± 13.69
Systolic BP (mmHg)	127.24 ± 20.87
Smoking status	
Never	168 (42%)
Former	94 (23.5%)
Current	138 (34.5%)
Diabetes	133 (33.3%)
Hypertension	182 (45.5%)
Hyperlipidemia	151 (37.8%)
Family history of CAD	89 (22.3%)
Killip class	
Class I	272 (68%)
Class II	87 (21.8%)
Class III	30 (7.5%)
Class IV	10 (2.5%)
Symptom-to-PCI time	
<3h	139 (34.8%)
3-6h	163 (40.8%)
>6h	98 (24.5%)
Infarct location	
Anterior	184 (46%)
Inferior	153 (38.3%)
Lateral	37 (9.3%)
Extensive	26 (6.5%)

After 24 hours, ST was resolved partially in 104 (26%) and completely in 244 (61%) patients. The mean baseline LVEF was 42.31 ± 7.75%. A

significant improvement was observed at 48 hours (45.89 ± 7.95%, p < 0.001) and at one-month follow-up (48.29 ± 8.17%, p < 0.001). The

mean increase in LVEF was 3.59% at 48 hours and 5.99% at one month. At 48 hours, the RWMA was improved in 167 (41.8%), worsened in 78 (19.5%) and there was no change in 155 (38.8%).

The 48-hour mean LVEF was similar for all groups ($F = 0.072$, $p = 0.931$). The Tukey HSD post hoc test revealed no pairwise differences; therefore, there is no clear association between ST-segment resolution and MACE ($\chi^2 = 11.377$, $p = 0.003$). Patients without ST-segment resolution had higher MACE rates (23.1%) than those with partial (7.7%) ST-segment resolution or complete (8.2%) ST-segment resolution.

A logistic regression analysis indicated that the model predicting MACE was statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 32.224$, $p < 0.001$), but exhibited only moderate predictive capability (Nagelkerke $R^2 = 0.162$). Killip class was identified as a statistically significant predictor of MACE (odds ratio (OR) 1.672, 95% CI 1.137 - 2.460, $p = 0.009$). Procedural success was also associated with significantly decreased odds of MACE (OR 0.156, 95% CIs 0.058 - 0.420, $p < 0.001$). Other variables (age, initial LVEF, ST resolution at 24 hours, and time from diagnosis to PCI) were not statistically significant predictors of MACE (Table 2).

Table 2: Multivariable logistic regression showing predictors of MACE.

Predictor	Adjusted OR	95% CI	p-value
Age	1.017	0.984-1.051	0.309
Baseline LVEF	1.041	0.993-1.092	0.093
Killip Class	1.672	1.137-2.460	0.009
ST-Resolution_24h	0.797	0.487-1.305	0.367
Procedural Success	0.156	0.058-0.420	<0.001
Symptom-to-PCI Time	0.68	0.426-1.084	0.105

Discussion

The aim of this study was to evaluate how primary PCI affected ECG and ECHO parameters among patients with STEMI and to further examine their relationship with short-term clinical outcomes. The study had three main findings. First, there was significant improvement in LV systolic function immediately after intervention or at 1-month follow-up, showing patients had significant recovery following reperfusion therapy. Second, no statistical correlation existed between ST segment resolution and early post-procedure LVEF, though ST segment resolution was previously viewed as a marker of successful reperfusion. Finally, results showed hemodynamic status and procedural success had greater impact on clinical outcome; Killip class and procedural success emerged as independent predictors of MACEs. At 48 hours and one month after primary PCI, patients showed increased LVEF, illustrating the benefits of early reperfusion therapy for STEMI

patients. Timely blood flow restoration decreases myocardial infarction size, protects viable myocardium, and helps restore stunned myocardial segments (16,17). Studies have shown stunning, not irreversible necrosis, causes transient post-ischemic decline in heart contractile function, with recovery occurring over days to weeks (18). Large studies of mechanical and pharmacological reperfusion have shown that appropriate reperfusion leads to improved LV function and decreased mortality risk (19,20). The gradual LVEF improvement is likely due to stunning recovery, improved wall motion, and early reverse remodeling, demonstrating the importance of rapid revascularization. Despite ST-segment resolution's acceptance as a marker of successful reperfusion, this study found no significant associations with early post-procedural LVEF. ST-segment resolution measures microvascular perfusion and electrical stability rather than mechanical recovery (21).

LVEF is influenced by infarction volume, myocardium viability, and LV properties. While previous studies showed ST-segment resolution relates to long-term outcome, the relationship to early LVEF varies, possibly due to timing of assessments, as early measures may not accurately reflect ultimate recovery of stunned myocardium (22).

Killip Class has become an independent risk factor for MACE and reflects the continuing relevance of this simple bedside tool for prognostication. The Killip classification depicts the extent of LV dysfunction, hemodynamic instability, and the amount of myocardial damage and is related to infarct severity (23). Multiple studies support using Killip Class as a reliable predictor of death and complications in patients with acute MI (24,25).

The significant protective effect of procedural success on MACE illustrates the importance of achieving an optimal reperfusion. Successful PCI restores epicardial flow as well as improves myocardial perfusion distal to the site of the blockage, thus limiting the amount of ischemic damage caused by the blockage (26). Numerous research studies have consistently shown that angiographic success, particularly the restoration of normal coronary flow, is associated with improved survival and decreased complication rates (27).

In regression analysis, age, baseline LVEF, time from symptom onset to PCI, and ST-segment resolution did not remain significant predictors of outcome. This may be the result of a low event rate, shorter follow-up, and/or interaction of variables (28). It is also possible that early invasive therapy mitigated the impact of traditional risk factors (29).

The results of this research have significant real-world implications, including a continued emphasis on using an early primary coronary intervention to successfully manage STEMI based on improved LV function. In addition, the Killip classification provides a quality and reliable prognostic predictor, while successful procedures represent a modifiable factor that significantly impacts patient outcomes. Resolution of ST segments is a clinically viable measure of

improvement; however, when combined with hemodynamics and procedure classification performance data, its clinical value will be maximized.

The analyses performed in this study support the conclusions, because of the reasonably high sample size and the multiple time periods for analysis of ECGs, echocardiogram, and clinical parameters. All studies conducted in this study were limited by being performed in single-center, having a 30-day follow-up period, and not including advanced technologies for further penis characterization. Residual confounding may not be excluded due to lack of advanced technologies.

Conclusion

Patients undergoing primary PCI following an acute STEMI show statistically significant improvement in LV systolic function shortly after the intervention occurs. Additionally, the results of this study indicate the most predictive factors, excluding ST segment markers are clinical and procedural hemodynamics. Therefore, integrated clinical and procedural assessment should continue to play an important role in predicting long-term outcomes following an acute STEMI event.

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